

Cascadia Region Earthquake Science Center

2024-25 Seed Grant Program Final Report

Tsunami Morphodynamics and Their Role in Hazard, Risk and Resilience Modulation and Environmental Impact in Newport, Oregon

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CRESCENT Seed Grant Program — FY2025 Final Report

Tsunami Morphodynamics and Their Role in Hazard, Risk and Resilience Modulation and Environmental Impact in Newport, Oregon

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CRESCENT pillar priorities addressed: Science – DET1 (tsunami models incorporating sediment transport, debris, and inundation) and CPAL2 (tsunami inundation near at-risk infrastructure); Partnerships & Applications – PA3 (translating science into action: loss modeling and resilience for the built environment).

1. Project accomplishments

The proposal posed one research question: how comprehensive modeling of the dynamic interactions among tsunami waves, sediment transport, and coastal morphology advances tsunami-impact assessment in Newport’s hybrid environment. It was organized under three objectives: (O1) quantify the effect of dynamic sediment transport and morphological change on inundation; (O2) evaluate the cumulative and cascading impacts on the hybrid environment; and (O3) translate those dynamics into resilience modeling. Objective O1 and the morphodynamic and infrastructure components of O2 were completed and form the basis of the manuscript now in review at *JGR: Earth Surface*. The resilience-integration objective (O3) was redirected toward a direct infrastructure-vulnerability and debris-management analysis, as described in Section 2.

Modeling framework (O1). A Delft3D-FM model (D-Flow hydrodynamics coupled with the D-Morphology sediment module) was built for an M_w 9.0 Cascadia Subduction Zone scenario, nested from a 2,187 m regional grid down to 1 m resolution across the Yaquina Bay estuary and run for a 3-hour tsunami sequence. Sediment was represented as a sand (267 μm) and mud mixture with spatially variable erodible-layer thickness (0.5–20 m), and surface roughness was assigned from NLCD land-cover classes (Manning n from 0.020 for open water to 0.180 for evergreen forest). A no-sediment baseline plus eight sediment-transport scenarios, spanning uniform versus spatially variable sediment thickness and roughness, were simulated to isolate the role of sediment dynamics and bracket uncertainty. Modeled inundation corresponded closely to the DOGAMI TIM ‘L’ scenario, supporting the model setup.

Key results (O1–O2). Sediment availability strongly modulated the hazard: scenarios with large sand reserves amplified local flood depths by up to +15 m and flow velocities by up to 10 m/s, exceeding

15 m/s at critical structures, while higher mud content and spatially variable roughness dampened these extremes. The simulations produced concentrated scour at exactly the locations occupied by critical infrastructure: up to -19.4 m of erosion at the North Jetty root, minima near -12 m at the Yaquina Bay Bridge piers, and -5 to -13 m at the marina, with deposition reaching $\sim 530,000$ m³ within the analysis area (Figure 1).

Scenario 3

Scenario 8

Figure 1. Cumulative morphology change for two representative active-morphology scenarios (Scenario 3, top; Scenario 8, bottom). Purple indicates erosion/scour; yellow–orange indicates deposition. Concentrated scour aligns with the North Jetty, the Yaquina Bay Bridge crossing, and the marina.

Infrastructure vulnerability translation. Three failure modes invisible to fixed-bed models were quantified: (i) North Jetty armor instability, evaluated with a Van der Meer damage parameter against a stability threshold for armor boulders ($D_{50} \approx 1.2$ m; boulder volumes of 1–8 m³ tested) (Figure 2) and supported by a field reconnaissance survey of the jetty root; (ii) bridge-pier scour at the Yaquina Bay Bridge; and (iii) potential unseating of the estuary water pipeline, where conservative and extreme post-tsunami seabed profiles were compared against the pipeline invert.

Scenario 3

Scenario 8

Figure 2. Hydrodynamic and morphological evolution for Scenarios 3 and 8. (Top Panel) Timeseries of water level (blue) and velocity (green) with morphological change (red dashed) on the secondary y-axis. (Bottom panel) Van der Meer's Damage Parameter S for tetrapods of varying volumes ($V = 1$ to 8 m^3) under tsunami loading. Markers indicate moments where $S > 3$, suggesting potential tetrapod detachment. Higher values of S in Scenario 3 indicate greater susceptibility to instability compared to Scenario 8.

Consequence and loss layer. Morphodynamic outputs were carried through to a debris-management and cascading-consequence assessment (Figure 3). Estimated deposition of 100,000 to more than 530,000 m^3 corresponds to roughly 10,000 to over 50,000 dump-truck loads of tsunami sediment—an order-of-magnitude cleanup liability of roughly \$8–38M (at ~\$50/ton)—before accounting for jetty, bridge, port, and utility damage.

Figure 3. Cascading-consequence chain linking tsunami hydro-/morphodynamics through physical failure modes (jetty breaching, scour, pipeline unseating, access loss) to lifeline degradation and economic and social disruption.

Principal finding. Fixed-bed models systematically and dangerously underestimate infrastructure risk in this setting. Sediment dynamics control both the spatial distribution and the severity of cascading failures, which has direct implications for hazard assessment, jetty rehabilitation prioritization, and utility routing.

2. What we did differently, and how we accounted for it

Two adjustments were made relative to the proposal, both to keep the work tractable and to maximize its applied value. Neither reduced the core scientific scope.

- **Objective O3 (resilience integration) was redirected.** The proposal called for integrating the morphodynamic results into the IN-CORE resilience-modeling environment to simulate recovery timelines. Establishing the upstream hazard and morphodynamic signal proved richer and more consequential than anticipated, so O3 was redirected from a formal IN-CORE coupling toward a direct infrastructure-vulnerability and debris-management analysis (jetty-armor stability, bridge and marina scour, and sediment-cleanup liability). This delivers the same PA3 intent while producing the validated hazard inputs a future IN-CORE integration will require.
- **Objective O2 roughness was parameterized differently.** Coastal-vegetation flow resistance was represented through NLCD land-cover-derived Manning roughness rather than the forest-specific *Trachytopes* parameterization originally proposed. This kept the eight-scenario matrix computationally feasible (individual runs ranged from ~15 hours to 8.3 days on HPC) while still capturing the first-order effect of roughness on flow and scour. Explicit forest-resolved flow resistance via *Trachytopes* is identified as a next step (Section 3).

Both were accommodated within the original budget and timeline, and the redirection of O3 strengthened the project's relevance to City of Newport and Port of Newport infrastructure priorities.

3. Next steps for this project

- Complete the resilience integration (O3): couple the validated morphodynamic and infrastructure-vulnerability outputs into the IN-CORE environment to model recovery timelines and community resilience, closing the loop on the original PA3 objective.
- Forest-resolved flow resistance (O2): implement the *Trachytopes* parameterization in Delft3D-FM to represent vegetation type, height, and density explicitly, and quantify how coastal forests modulate inundation and sediment transport.
- Validation and probabilistic extension: benchmark the morphodynamic results against paleotsunami and event-deposit constraints and couple the framework to probabilistic CSZ source ensembles and far-field tsunamis so scour and deposition can be expressed with recurrence-aware uncertainty.
- Structure-resolving (building-aware) modeling: extend the building-aware / dynamic-collapse capability developed alongside this grant to the tsunami-morphodynamics setting, so that flow, bed change, and the built environment are represented jointly.

- Integration and applied translation: contribute the model and scenario outputs to the appropriate CRESCENT resource under FAIR principles, and work with the City of Newport, port operators, and USACE to apply scour-aware results to jetty reinforcement, bridge-scour countermeasures, and pipeline routing.

4. Publications

Primary output (in review). Velasco-Reyes, E., Cox, D., & Barbosa, A. “Modeling Tsunami-Induced Sediment Transport and Erosion with Implications for Coastal Infrastructure Vulnerabilities.” *Journal of Geophysical Research: Earth Surface*, in review (Paper #2026JF009126).

Presentations:

- Velasco-Reyes, E., Cox, D., & Barbosa, A. “Tsunami morphodynamics and its effects on hazard modulation and critical infrastructure fragility” CRESCENT Annual Meeting, Seattle, Oct 28 & 29, 2025.
- Velasco-Reyes, E., Cox, D., & Barbosa, A. “Building-Aware Flood and Lifeline Scour Modeling with Delft3D FM: Hurricane Ian & Cascadia Tsunami.” Delft3D-FM Days. Delft, Netherlands. November, 2025.
- Velasco-Reyes, E., Cox, D., & Barbosa, A. “Tsunami Morphodynamics and Their Role in Hazard, Risk and Resilience Modulation and Environmental Impact in Newport.” CRESCENT Spring Virtual Session, April 21, 2026.

Related output enabled by this award. Resources and methods developed under this seed grant supported a companion structure-resolving study: Velasco-Reyes, E., Cox, D., & Barbosa, A. “Modeling building-aware overland flow and dynamic collapse during hurricane surge.” *Coastal Engineering* (2026). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coastaleng.2026.105014>

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